

Measurement of Energy Dependency and Efficiency in Asia: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

Energy dependency and efficiencies are the two important components under the concept of energy security. Availability and access to energy is pre-requisite for the functioning of any system, sector, and region which invariably demands energy security. Having this, in the present study an attempt has made to analyze energy dependency and energy efficiency in South Asia. Time series data have been used for the study and energy indices have computed. Energy dependency and efficiency have been measured for the South Asian countries. It has found from the study that energy dependency has shown a declining trend. The positive aspect is that energy efficiency has increased in all these countries. Interestingly, Nepal has a very positively increasing energy security trends. Therefore, Nepal will have better energy security shortly. Accordingly, to improve the energy security of South Asia, the energy dependency on other countries has to be reduced. At the same time, energy efficiency has to be further improved, so that it has a positive influence on energy security. It has been proved by many studies that there is a positive long-run stable relationship between energy and development. Accordingly, energy security is a pre-requisite for development. Having all these valued arguments, the study thinks that energy security, more specifically, self-sufficient and efficient energy security plays a vital and critical role in the development of South Asian countries.

Keywords: Energy Security, Energy Dependency and Energy Efficiency, JLE

Classification: Q.4, O.53, P.48

Introduction

Energy Dependency refers to the dependence of one country on other countries for its energy requirements and energy efficiency refers to increase of output without increasing the energy use or decrease in energy use to produce the same level of output. Energy is critical for all activities starting from consumption to production and even for human development (Premakumara, 2012). Ever increasing demand for energy, de-carbonization of energy system, unequal distribution of energy resources, need for efficient use of energy, international agreements and treaties on energy, emerge of Asian tigers, emerging of middle class particularly in Asia, sustainability issues have led the academicians' to have intensified studies and research on energy

security issues. On the lighter side, the present study will have a bird's eye view on energy efficiency and dependency. At the same time, the objective of the present research work is to estimate and analyze the energy dependency and efficiency in South Asia and to draw specific policy imperatives for better energy security.

Review of Literature

There are two sets of distinct arguments related to energy and development. The first set of argument is energy has a significant impact on production which will result in the development (Masih A. M., 1996) (Asafu-Adjaye, 2000). Because without energy the other inputs like labor and capital may not be used. However, the contribution of energy to the development varies based on the availability and efficient use of energy. Therefore, energy has been considered as a factor in development. The other argument is energy is not at all a factor of production since the value of energy in total production is very negligible. Therefore, energy may not play a significant role in the development process (Cheng, 1995) (Yu E. J., 1992). Energy is essential for development, whereas, eco-efficient and clean energy is critical for sustainable development. Adequate and reliable and affordable energy is the pre-requisite for development (Premakumara, 2012). Another important dimension argues that there has been a significant association between energy efficiency and development (Sascha & Andreas, 2015) (Sreenivas, 2014). Most of the early literature on causation of economic growth on energy consumption have confirmed the causation by using uni-directional Granger- Causality Tests (Yu E., 1984) (Kraft J. K., 1978) (Lin, 2003) (Soytas, 2003) (Mozumdar, 2007). During late 90's the economists like Nachane and others have employed Engel-Granger Models to estimate the causation of electricity and energy on economic growth (Nachane, 1988) (Masih, 1996) (Glasure, 1997) (Asafu-Adjaye, 2000) (Thoma, 2004) (Hansen, 2002) (Yoo, 2005). Meanwhile, the co-integration techniques were also used to estimate the long-run relationship between energy consumption and economic growth. Jumbe and Huang have proved the bi-directional relationship between energy consumption and economic growth (Jumbe, 2004) (Huang, 2008). Estimation of the multi-dimensional relationship has also proved the role of energy in overall economic development (Tamizan, 2009) (Shahbaz, 2012). Recently, Sadorsky has proved the influence of financial development on energy consumption (Sadorsky, 2010). Very recently, the ARDL bounds test was used to prove the causation of energy demand on export (shahbaz, 2013).

There is a need for stable energy security in a country to have sustainable, balanced economic development. Since the concept of energy security is more complex, multidimensional, and contextual, most of the previous studies have tried to define the concept of energy security (Bohi & Toman, 1996) (Baldwin, 1997). Recent studies have tried to estimate and forecast energy security (Kamonphorn & Hironobu, 2014) (Ito, Zhidong, & Komiyama, 2005). Few studies have also tried to develop the dimensions and indicators to measure energy security (Lixia & Youngho, 2014). However, there are no unique studies to specifically define and estimate the energy dependency and efficiency particularly for South Asian countries by using time series data and the present study is a step forward in this direction.

Measurement of Energy Security

Previous researchers have used all together 35 indicators to measure energy security of a country. As mentioned earlier, energy security is multi-dimensional, contextual and subjective. Lixia Yao and Youngho Chang have used four dimension and 20 indicators to measure China's energy security. Kamonphorn Kanchana and Hironobu Unesakia have used six dimensions and almost equal indicators to measure energy security. Jeffrey Kucharski, Hironobu Unesaki have developed

energy security system to analyze the energy security of a country. Premakumara G.S. used four dimensions and eight indicators to measure energy security. The close observation of previous studies indicates that the four important aspects have been covered in measuring energy security, and they are; economic, environmental, technology and society. Under the economic aspect, the availability of energy and supply of energy have been discussed. Under the environmental aspect, extraction of energy, transmission, renewable energies, carbon emission and energy conservation have been discussed. Under the technology aspect, energy efficiency, imports, dependency of a country on another country for its energy need and other issues have been discussed. Under the last aspect the society, energy acceptability of a society, per-capita consumption and pricing mechanisms have been discussed. In the present study, I have used five dimensions and six indicators to measure the energy security by using the index method. However, the present study is unique in its methodological issues and model building which the previous studies have not followed.

Methodology

The study is confined to South Asian countries namely; Bangladesh (BGD), Nepal (NPL), Indonesia (IDN), India (IND), Sri Lanka (LKA) and Pakistan (PAK) only and used secondary time series data. Data have collected from World Development Bank Data Base. To index, methods have been calculating energy security and data presented in the form of graphs and tables (processed). The major dimension and parameters used in the study are;

Dimension	Index	Indicator	Working Definition	Index Formula
Dependency	Energy Dependency Index	Import of Energy: Negative Indicator	% of energy imported in total consumption	Energy Dependency Index = $\frac{((\text{Max}-\text{Actual})/(\text{Max}-\text{Min}))}{\text{Max} = 100, \text{Min} = 0}$
Efficiency	Energy Efficiency Index	Energy Intensity: Negative Indicator	Energy Used to Produce one Unit of GDP (MJ/2011 USD PPP)	Energy Efficiency Index = $\frac{((\text{Max}-\text{Actual})/(\text{Max}-\text{Min}))}{\text{Max} = 10.41, \text{Min} = 2.19}$

Energy Security index is a composite index computed by using five-dimensional indices.

Energy Security index = Geometric Mean of (Energy Dependency Index and Energy Efficiency Index)

ANOVA and multiple Duncan range tests used for comparison of an energy security index and indices among the countries. Correlation co-efficient matrix computed to establish the relationship between energy security and dimensions of energy security.

Analysis of Energy Dependency

Energy dependency has measured in terms of import as a percentage of the total energy of a country. There is an inverse relationship between dependency and energy security. As energy dependency increases, energy security will be reduced. The trends in energy dependency index have computed for each year by using time series data from 1991 to 2012 and presented in the following graph.

Graph 1: Trends in Energy Dependency Index

Source: World Development Bank Data Base.

The above graph presents trends in energy dependency index. It has observed from the above graph that the energy dependency index has shown a negative trend for all the countries. Therefore, energy dependency has been increased in all these countries and it will have a negative impact on the energy security of these countries. Accordingly, to ensure energy security, there is a need for these countries to reduce the energy dependency on other countries and develop internal energy sources to improve energy production and security.

Table 1 Energy Dependency in South Asia (In Index Value)

Countries	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
BNG	22	.8336	.02647	.00564	.78	.87
NPL	22	.8982	.02403	.00512	.84	.94
IDN	22	.8200	.08159	.01740	.68	.92
IND	22	.7941	.06107	.01302	.68	.89
LKA	22	.5995	.07034	.01500	.51	.75
PAK	22	.7668	.02679	.00571	.72	.82
Total	132	.7854	.10667	.00928	.51	.94
F-Value: 78.004***				Sig: 0.000		

Source: World Development Bank Data Base.

The above table presents average energy dependency of six South Asian countries. The lowest energy dependency index was found for Sri Lanka and highest energy dependency index was found for Nepal. The least average energy dependency index in 22 years was also found for Sri Lanka and the highest average energy dependency index in 22 years was also found for Nepal. There are differences in average energy dependency index among the South Asian countries and it has found from the ANOVA test that these differences are significant at one percent level. However, which countries are significantly differing from others is not found from the ANOVA test. Hence, in the following table, multiple comparisons Duncan test has computed.

Table 2 Multiple Comparisons for Energy Dependency in South Asia (In Index Value)

Countries	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05				
		1	2	3	4	5
LKA	22	.5995				
PAK	22		.7668			
IND	22		.7941	.7941		
IDN	22			.8200	.8200	
BNG	22				.8336	
NPL	22					.8982
Sig.		1.000	.095	.112	.402	1.000
Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.						
a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 22.000.						

Source: World Development Bank Data Base.

It has found from subsets of Duncan test that energy dependency index is significantly high for Nepal followed by Bangladesh, Indonesia, India, and Pakistan. At the same time, energy dependency index is significantly low for Sri Lanka. Therefore, energy dependency is significantly high in Sri Lanka among Asian countries.

Analysis of Energy Efficiency

Energy efficiency has measured in terms of intensity of energy i.e., amount of energy used to produce one unit of output or GDP. There is an inverse relationship between the use of energy and energy efficiency security. As energy intensity in production reduces energy efficiency will be improved and it will be positively resulted in energy security. The trends in energy efficiency index have computed for each year by using time series data from 1991 to 2012 and presented in the following graph.

Graph 2: Trends in Energy Efficiency Index

Source: World Development Bank Data Base.

The above graph presents trends in energy efficiency index. It has observed from the above graph that the energy efficiency index has shown a positive trend for all the countries. Therefore, energy efficiency has been increased in all these countries and it will have a positive impact on the energy security of these countries. Accordingly, to ensure energy security, there is a need to further reduce the energy intensity to improve energy efficiency and security.

Table 3 Energy Efficiency in South Asia (In Index Value)

Countries	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Minimum	Maximum
BNG	22	.9036	.02735	.00583	.86	.94
NPL	22	.1773	.09977	.02127	.01	.39
IDN	22	.8377	.04219	.00900	.77	.92
IND	22	.7232	.12541	.02674	.49	.88
LKA	22	.9000	.06024	.01284	.80	1.00
PAK	22	.7655	.02614	.00557	.73	.82
Total	132	.7179	.26164	.02277	.01	1.00
F-Value: 305.699***				Sig: 0.000		

Source: World Development Bank Data Base.

The above table presents the average energy efficiency of six South Asian countries. The lowest energy efficiency index was found for Nepal and highest energy efficiency index was found for Sri Lanka. The least average energy efficiency index in 22 years was also found for Nepal and the highest average energy efficiency index in 22 years was found for Bangladesh. There are differences in average energy efficiency index among the South Asian countries and it has found from the ANOVA test that these differences are significant at one percent level. However, which countries are significantly differing from others is not found from the ANOVA test. Hence, in the following table, multiple comparisons Duncan test has computed.

Table 4 Multiple Comparisons for Energy Efficiency in South Asia (In Index Value)

Countries	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05			
		1	2	3	4
NPL	22	.1773			
IND	22		.7232		
PAK	22		.7655		
IDN	22			.8377	
LKA	22				.9000
BNG	22				.9036
Sig.		1.000	.059	1.000	.870
Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.					
a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 22.000.					

Source: World Development Bank Data Base.

It has found from subsets of Duncan test that energy efficiency index is significantly high for Bangladesh and Sri Lanka followed by Indonesia, Pakistan and India. At the same time, energy efficiency index is significantly low for Nepal. Therefore, energy Efficiency is significantly high in Bangladesh and Sri Lanka among Asian countries.

Conclusion

In the present study, an attempt has been made to examine the energy dependency and efficiency of South Asian countries. It has found from the study that energy dependency has shown a declining trend. The positive aspect is that energy efficiency has increased in all these countries. Interestingly, Nepal has a very positively increasing energy security trends. Therefore, Nepal will have better energy security shortly. Accordingly, to improve the energy security of South Asia, the energy dependency on other countries has to be reduced. At the same time, energy efficiency has to be further improved, so that it has a positive influence on energy security. It has been proved by

many studies that there is a positive long-run stable relationship between energy and development. Accordingly, energy security is a pre-requisite for development. Having all these valued arguments, the study thinks that energy security, more specifically, self-sufficient and efficient energy security plays a vital and critical role in the development of South Asian countries.

References

1. Asafu-Adjaye. (2000). The relationship between energy consumption, energy prices, and economic growth: time series evidence from Asian developing countries. *Energy Economics*, 22, 615-625.
2. Asafu-Adjaye, J. (2000). The relationship between energy consumption, energy prices, and economic growth: time series evidence from Asian developing countries. *Energy Economics*, 22, 615-625.
3. Baldwin, D. A. (1997). The Concept of Energy Security. *Rev. Int. Stud.* 23, 5-26.
4. Bohi, D., & Toman, M. A. (1996). *The Economics of Energy Security*. Norwell, Massachusetts: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
5. Cheng, B. (1995). An investigation of cointegration and causality between energy consumption and economic growth. *Journal of Energy Development*, 21, 73-84.
6. Glasure, Y. L. (1997). Cointegration, error correction and the relationship between GDP and energy: the case of South Korea and Singapore. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 20, 17-25.
7. Hancock, K., & Vivoda, V. (2014). International Political Economy: A Feld Born of the OPEC Crisis Returns to its Energy Roots. *Energy Research. Social Science*, 1, 206–216.
8. Hansen, B. S. (2002). Testing for two-regime threshold cointegration in vector error-correction models. *Journal Of Econometrics* 110, 293-318.
9. Huang, B. H. (2008). The causal relationship between energy consumption and GDP growth revisited: a dynamic panel data approach. *Ecological Economics*, 67, 41-54.
10. Ito, K., Zhidong, L., & Komiyama, R. (2005). Asian Energy Outlook up to 2020. *Economic and Political Weekly* September 3, 3953-3959.
11. Jeffrey, K., & Hironobu, U. (2015). A policy-oriented approach to energy security. *Procedia Environmental Sciences* 28, 27 – 36.
12. Jumbe, C. (2004). Cointegration and causality between electricity consumption and GDP: empirical evidence from Malawi. *Energy Economics*, 26, 61-68.
13. Kamonphorn, K., & Hironobu, U. (2014). ASEAN Energy Security: An indicator-based Assessment. *Energy Procedia* 56, 163 – 171.
14. Kamonphorn, K., & Hironobu, U. B. (2014). ASEAN Energy Security: An Indicator-Based Assessment. *Energy Procedia* 56, 163 – 171.
15. Kokichi Ito, L. Z., & Komiyama, R. (2005). Asian Energy Outlook up to 2020. *Economic and Political Weekly* XLI (16), 3953-3959.
16. Kraft, J. K. (1978). On the relationship between energy and GNP. *Energy Development*, 3, 401–403.
17. Lin, B. (2003). Structural change, efficiency improvement and electricity demand forecasting (In Chinese. *Economic Research*, 5, 57-65.
18. Lixia, Y., & Youngho, C. (2014). Energy Security in China; A Quantitative Analysis and Policy Implications. *Energy Policy* 67, 595-604.

Web Sources

1. https://www.dghs.gov.in/content/1313_4_fromdgdsk.aspx
2. <https://www.econ.cmu.ac.th/econadmin/files/2559/aed/Full%20Proceeding%20-%20AED2016.pdf>